

THE CONCEPT AND HISTORY OF CULTURAL HERITAGE

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Annotation: This article provides information about the cultural heritage. Cultural heritage refers to the physical and intangible elements of a society's culture, which are inherited from past generations and are valued for their cultural significance. Cultural heritage plays a crucial role in preserving and promoting a society's identity and history. It serves as a means of communication between generations by passing down knowledge, customs, traditions, and artistic expressions. It also contributes to the socio-economic development of a community, attracting tourists and promoting local businesses

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Cultural heritage refers to the traditions, customs, beliefs, practices, and artifacts passed down from one generation to another within a certain cultural group or community. These cultural artifacts and practices form an essential part of the identity and history of a community or society and are manifestations of its shared heritage. Cultural heritage encompasses tangible and intangible aspects that are passed on from one generation to another, including art, language, music, dance, literature, architecture, and historical sites. In addition, cultural heritage refers to the legacy of cultural and natural artifacts, places, and traditions that have been inherited from previous generations and preserved for future generations. This includes tangible artifacts such as buildings, artifacts, and artistic works, as well as intangible cultural heritage such as oral traditions, languages, festivals, and cultural practices. Moreover, cultural heritage is an important aspect of human history and identity, as it reflects the values, beliefs, and traditions of a particular group of people. Cultural heritage objects are symbolic. They represent identities in terms of culture and natural surroundings. Connection to and traditional activities around these objects create a sense of community. At the same time, the selection of which objects, monuments or natural environments are preserved sets the future trajectory for various cultural narratives and societal consensus about both the past and present. Cultural heritage has a long history that dates back to ancient civilizations, where artifacts and practices were passed down from one generation to another. Throughout history, different societies have placed high importance on preserving their cultural heritage, and this has led to the creation of museums, national parks, historical monuments, and other preservation efforts to safeguard their cultural heritage for future generations.

The concept of cultural heritage was formalized in the 19th century with the emergence of a more critical and scientific approach to history. This led to the creation of institutions such as national museums, archives, and libraries for the preservation of cultural heritage. UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) has played a critical role in the preservation of cultural heritage since its creation in 1945, working to protect historical sites and artifacts from destruction caused by war, natural disasters, and human activities such as pollution and urbanization. Historically, the concept of cultural heritage dates back to

the 19th century when the industrial revolution resulted in significant changes in society, including urbanization, mass production, and the growth of consumer culture. During this period, there was a growing concern that traditional cultures and practices were being lost due to modernization and industrialization. The first efforts to preserve cultural heritage were made in the late 1800s and early 1900s, with the establishment of museums and national libraries in Europe and North America. The work of archaeologists, anthropologists, and historians focused on the rediscovery and preservation of ancient ruins, manuscripts, and works of art. In the 20th century, cultural heritage preservation became an international concern, following the destruction of numerous cultural sites during World War II. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) was established in 1945, and in 1954 it adopted the Convention for the Protection of Cultural Property in the Event of Armed Conflict. This convention aimed at protecting cultural heritage during wartime.

In 1972, UNESCO adopted the Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, which established the World Heritage List, a catalogue of sites that possess outstanding universal cultural and natural value, and which require protection for future generations. As of 2021, there are 1,121 sites included in the World Heritage List. It is clear that, the concept of cultural heritage has evolved over time, with different societies and cultures placing varying degrees of importance on preserving their heritage. In ancient civilizations, cultural heritage was often associated with religious or spiritual beliefs, and monuments and artifacts were created to honor gods and goddesses. In medieval Europe, cultural heritage was often associated with the ruling class, and castles, palaces, and other grand buildings were constructed to demonstrate wealth and power.

In the modern era, cultural heritage has become a more widely recognized concept, with many countries and organizations working to preserve and protect their cultural heritage. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) promotes international cooperation in the fields of education, science, and culture, and to protect cultural heritage sites around the world. UNESCO has designated numerous sites as World Heritage Sites, which are considered to be of outstanding cultural or natural importance to humanity. The preservation of cultural heritage is important for several reasons. It helps to maintain a sense of identity and continuity within a community, and it can also promote tourism and economic development. Additionally, cultural heritage can provide valuable insights into the history and evolution of human societies, and can help to foster cross-cultural understanding and appreciation. However, cultural heritage is also vulnerable to destruction and loss, whether through natural disasters, war, or neglect, and it is important to take steps to protect and preserve it for future generations.

Overall, the importance of cultural heritage lies not only in preserving a community's identity and history but also in promoting cultural diversity and fostering a sense of understanding and respect for other cultures and communities. And also, the concept of cultural heritage evolved as a response to the need to preserve traditional cultures and practices that were threatened by the rapid changes brought by industrialization and modernization. Today, cultural heritage preservation is a global concern, and efforts are being made to preserve this legacy for future generations

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